

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL GEL FOR ANTI-ITCHING AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The present study was aimed at the formulation and evaluation of a polyherbal gel containing Aloe vera and Tulsi for anti-itching and anti-inflammatory activity. Herbal formulations are gaining importance due to their safety, effectiveness, and minimal side effects compared to synthetic drugs. Aloe vera is well known for its soothing, moisturizing, and healing properties, while Tulsi possesses antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities. The gel was prepared using Carbopol 940 as a gelling agent along with suitable excipients like glycerin, methyl paraben, and triethanolamine. The prepared formulations were evaluated for various parameters such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, homogeneity, and stability. The results showed that the formulated gel exhibited good physicochemical properties, excellent

spreadability, and stability without phase separation. Thus, the polyherbal gel can be considered a safe and effective natural remedy for the management of itching and inflammation.

KEYWORDS: Polyherbal gel, Aloe vera, Tulsi, Anti-itching, Anti-inflammatory, Herbal formulation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Skin disorders such as itching, irritation, and inflammation are very common and can be caused by infections, allergies, insect bites, and environmental factors. These conditions lead to discomfort, redness, and swelling.

Synthetic topical preparations are widely used but often cause side effects like skin irritation and dryness. Therefore, herbal formulations are preferred due to their safety and compatibility with skin.

Polyherbal formulations provide a synergistic effect, enhancing therapeutic activity. Aloe vera and Tulsi are well-known medicinal plants used traditionally for treating skin problems due to their anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and soothing properties.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The present study was carried out to formulate and evaluate a polyherbal gel for anti-itching and anti-inflammatory activity. The selected herbal ingredients, Aloe vera gel and Tulsi leaves, were procured from a reliable local source and authenticated.

Aloe Vera

Synonym: Ghritkumari

Biological Source: Obtained from leaves of *Aloe barbadensis* Miller

Family: Liliaceae

Chemical Constituents: Vitamins (A, C, E), enzymes, polysaccharides, aloin, flavonoids

Pharmacological Activity: Anti-inflammatory, wound healing, moisturizing, anti-itching.

Tulsi

Synonym: Holy Basil

Biological Source: Leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn.

Family: Lamiaceae

Chemical Constituents Eugenol, flavonoids, tannins, essential oils

Pharmacological Activity: Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-allergic

Method of Preparation

Fresh Aloe vera leaves were collected and gel was extracted.

Tulsi leaves were shade-dried and powdered.

Tulsi extract was prepared using maceration method.

Carbopol 940 was dispersed in distilled water and allowed to swell.

Aloe vera gel and Tulsi extract were added to the Carbopol base.

Glycerin was added as a humectant.

Methyl paraben was added as a preservative.

Triethanolamine was added dropwise to adjust pH and form gel.

The gel was mixed properly to obtain a uniform consistency.

The prepared gel was stored in airtight containers.

Formulation

S.no	Formulation	Aloe vera	Tulsi	Carbopol	Glycerin
1	F1	10gm	5gm	1gm	2ml
2	F2	12gm	4gm	1gm	2ml
3	F3	8gm	6gm	1gm	2ml

Evaluation Parameters

pH Determination

S. no	Formulation	pH
1	F1	5.8
2	F2	6.0
3	F3	5.7

Viscosity

S.no	Formulation	Viscosity (CPS)
1	F1	3200
2	F2	3100
3	F3	3300

Spreadability

S. no	Formulation	Spreadability
1	F1	Good
2	F2	Good
3	F3	Good

Homogeneity

All formulations showed good homogeneity without lumps.

Stability Study

All formulations were stable at 40°C with no change in color, odor, or consistency.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The formulated polyherbal gel was evaluated for physicochemical and organoleptic properties. All three formulations (F1, F2, F3) showed acceptable results.

The gel had a smooth texture, good spreadability, and suitable pH for skin application. The viscosity indicated proper consistency for topical use. The presence of Aloe vera provided a soothing effect, while Tulsi contributed antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activity.

Among all batches, F1 formulation showed the best overall performance in terms of stability, consistency, and effectiveness.

Table no 1: Evaluation Results.

Parameter	F1	F2	F3
pH	5.8	6.0	5.7
Viscosity	3200cps	3100cps	3300cps
Spread ability	Good	Good	Good
Stability	Stable	Stable	Stable

Table no. 2: Organoleptic Properties.

Parameter	F1	F2	F3
Color	Light green	Light green	Light green
Odor	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic
Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth

4. CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated a polyherbal gel containing Aloe vera and Tulsi for anti-itching and anti-inflammatory activity.

The formulation showed good physicochemical properties, stability, and skin compatibility. The synergistic effect of Aloe vera and Tulsi provides soothing, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory benefits.

Thus, the developed polyherbal gel can be considered a safe, effective, and natural alternative to synthetic topical formulations. Further clinical studies are recommended to confirm its therapeutic efficacy.

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